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D2.4 Policy making processes blueprints V1 – Resubmission

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
ML	Machine Learning
DL	Deep Learning
DB	Database
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	AI4PublicPolicy
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

Executive summary

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies.

The present document, D2.4 “Policy making processes blueprints V1”, has been authored within the framework of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”. The objectives of WP2 are to identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners (i.e., five European cities) and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy, review current standards and regulations, analyse current policy making processes, define data models and datasets used within the project, and finally specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform. All activities follow a co-creation process involving the five pilot cities, i.e., Athens, Lisbon, Nicosia, Genoa and Burgas.

The purpose of D2.4 “Policy making processes blueprints V1” is to capture the existing processes from the five pilot cities in relation to the use cases that will form the basis for the pilot activities within AI4PP. These use cases are:

- Maintenance policies optimization and Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development (Athens)
- Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization (Genoa), including:
 - Identification and Benchmarking of new Buildings for hosting the electoral operations & provision of information for facilitating the smooth access to such facilities
 - Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems
 - More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations.
- Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility (Nicosia)
- Energy Management and Optimization Policies (Lisbon)
- Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies (Burgas)

Initial ideas on how said processes could be enhanced and improved through the proposed AI solutions are also included per city.

This is the first of two versions this document will be delivered in. Subsequent versions will also include blueprints for reengineering policy making processes and supporting employees of the public administration accordingly, also capturing the interactions between different roles in the public administration domain as well as between public administrators and the local ecosystem.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management”

The objectives of WP2 are to:

- Specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform by identifying components, their functionalities and interconnection, ensuring their coherency with the requirements and global architecture.
- Identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Review the standards and regulations and identify appropriate ones that need to be monitored and followed in the project.
- Analyse the policy making processes to ensure that the outcomes of the project address and enhance/improve these processes, while reducing the bottlenecks in public administration and ensuring high quality and adoption of results.
- Define the data models of the datasets to be utilized for the development, training and actual utilization of the AI models and algorithms of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Define the co-creation process.

1.3 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this document is to capture the existing processes from the five pilot cities, namely Athens, Genoa, Nicosia, Lisbon and Burgas, in relation to the use cases that will form the basis for the pilot activities within AI4PP. Initial ideas on how said processes could be enhanced and improved through the proposed AI solutions are also included per city.

This is the first of two versions this document will be delivered in. Subsequent versions will also include blueprints for reengineering policy making processes and supporting employees of the public administration accordingly, also capturing the interactions between different roles in the public administration domain as well as between public administrators and the local ecosystem.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D2.4 “Policy making processes blueprints V1” comprises of five chapters, each dedicated to one of the AI4PP pilot cities, namely Athens, Genoa, Nicosia, Lisbon and Burgas. For each city, an overview of the pilot use cases is provided, along with the current processes related to these use cases and the respective roles of stakeholders involved. Initial ideas on how said processes could be enhanced and improved through the proposed AI solutions are also included per city. The document also includes an introductory chapter (Chapter 1), providing basic information regarding the AI4PublicPolicy project, a brief description of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”, the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable. The final chapter includes the document conclusions.

2 Athens: Management and Optimization of City Resources

2.1 Overview of the Use Case

The Athens pilot aims at developing, demonstrating and evaluating data-driven, citizen-centric and evidence-based policies about the maintenance of the city's infrastructure and the citizens' transport and urban mobility, including the economic implications of these policies. The pilot comprises of two use cases:

- **Maintenance policies optimization.** This use case will develop and validate policies for the optimal allocation of maintenance resources (e.g., workers, vehicles, materials), as well as for scheduling of different maintenance activities in the city.
- **Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development.** This use case will be based on the execution of AI analytics over transport data (notably parking information) as a means of providing citizens with prediction about parking availability in the different areas of the city, as well as on providing to the city a tool for optimal use of city-parking resources.

Both use cases will be expanded with information about the city's revenues from the parking and the maintenance planning. In particular, the policy models of the previous use cases will be augmented with fiscal/monetary parameters in order to identify policies that maximize the city's revenues from the parking service, while minimizing the cost of the maintenance, service and repair activities.

2.2 Relevant processes

2.2.1 Maintenance policies optimization

The current process for reporting and handling maintenance issues is depicted in the following figure and comprises of the following steps:

1. **A report is inserted into the platform.** The platform administrator inserts in the platform reports that have been initiated via phone call, email, personal contact by a citizen or internal suggestion by another agency of the Municipality. Reports initiated through the mobile application or the webapp are inserted in the platform automatically.

Each report includes information regarding the identity of the person initiating the report, the location, the incident category, the current status (e.g., in progress, finished), a description and photo and other details.
2. **The report is processed by the administrator.** Processing enables the administrator to modify the report information, forward it to the appropriate agency for resolution, communicate with the citizen that initiated the report or print the report.
3. **The report is resolved by the appropriate agency employees.** Depending on their category, reports are forwarded to the appropriate agency to be resolved. Each agency has a different internal process for handling reports. As soon as the agency employees (work team) resolve the issue, they notify the agency, and the administrator updates the report status in the platform.
4. **The citizen is informed about the report's resolution.** Citizens are notified through the app about the resolution of their report.

Figure 2. Reporting and handling maintenance issues in Athens

The administrator has additional tools available through the platform for managing the reports. These include:

- A **Dashboard**, presenting an overview of reports, statistics, resolution times, report frequency, etc.
- A **Map**, presenting reports based on their location and their current status.
- An **optimal route functionality**, through which a route among reports is proposed to the work team for reaching them in the best possible way, based on location, traffic data, etc.

2.2.2 Predictive Citizen-Centric Transport/Parking Policies Development

The current parking management application enables citizens to purchase parking tickets for specific locations for up to three hours.

The platform includes a dedicated mobile application for Municipal Police employees that enables them to check whether a parked vehicle has issued a parking ticket or not and issue a fine on the spot. All checks and fines are entered real time into the Municipal Police platform.

Figure 3. The parking management application in Athens

2.3 Related roles

The related roles per Use Case currently include:

Table 1. Athens Pilot roles

Maintenance Reports Application	Parking Application
Head of Civil Protection and Electronic Citizen Service Department	Deputy mayor of Municipal Police Agency
Civil Protection and Electronic Citizen Service Department	Head of Municipal Police Agency
Waste Management Agency	Municipal policemen
Road Construction Agency	Citizens / Drivers
Agency of Social Affairs	
Agency for Green spaces and urban fauna	
Agency of Electrical Management	
Citizens/ Residents	

2.4 Future process improvements using AI4PP

The outcomes of AI4PP are expected to significantly improve not only the maintenance policies of the Municipality of Athens, but also the parking policies, and the way citizens experience parking around the city.

Utilizing the abundance of data collected through the Novoville Athens application will contribute to the optimal planning and allocation of maintenance resources, as well as preparatory actions (e.g., annual purchases) or scheduling of different activities in the city. The platform will take into account parameters such as the type of infrastructure, the time needed for repair, the frequency of maintenance problems of specific types and in specific locations, possible bottlenecks, as well as citizens’ feedback on their satisfaction from the maintenance process and outcomes. Redesigned policies are expected to reduce time in resolving reported incidents, reduce the average cost per incident for the city and increase citizen satisfaction from the infrastructure maintenance activities.

Taking into account historical data about utilization of parking spaces (peak hours, preferred locations, average time parked, etc.), parking spaces availability, fines imposed, fares paid and more, the AI4PublicPolicy tools will be used to recommend to citizens optimal tactics for finding parking spaces (e.g., locations with high availability), as well as for optimizing their parking payments (i.e., fares during specific times of day and for specific locations). Policies for the allocation of parking spaces between visitors and residents, as well as different pricing policies will also be recommended through AI4PublicPolicy tools. Redesigned policies are expected to increase citizen satisfaction from the smart parking activities, increased revenue from parking, improve average parking availability and improve “fill rate” and occupancy of available parking positions.

3 Genoa: Policies for Citizens and Business Services Optimization

3.1 Overview of the Use Case

The pilot will develop a policy development toolkit for the city of Genova, which will enable the public authority to extract and experiment with evidence-based policies about how to optimally organize the operations of the various citizen facing services and department of the municipality.

The following use cases have been identified:

- **Use Case #1. Identification and Benchmarking of new Buildings for hosting the electoral operations & provision of information for facilitating the smooth access to such facilities.** ML/DL techniques will be used to extract indications, provide recommendations and assessment on the identification of the new election facilities. In this process, several factors will be taken into account, including the official selection criteria, the central government's indications, the data about citizens' and municipal offices' requests/expectations, and citizens' satisfaction feedback.
- **Use Case #2. Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems.** ML/DL techniques will be employed over data about the citizens' requests for services and their handling workflows, in view of identifying optimal allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware). Two offices will be involved: social services office and demographic services office. As for the former, efforts will also include the improvement of the interoperability with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs), for the efficiency of resources and the development of evidence-based policies. As for the latter, the focus will be on the analysis and re-engineering of the transversal work process dealing in particular with registry office changes.
- **Use Case #3. More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the "SegnalaCI" Citizens' Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations.** This use case refers to the improvement of the planning and deployment of extraordinary maintenance interventions by using the SegnalaCI platform. Such platform allows to visualize data about citizens' suggestions/requests and reports, as well as about the workflows for handling the suggestions/requests in an interactive map/dashboard. Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each request will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens. The dashboard will be used to increase the transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of the policy development process

3.2 Relevant processes

3.2.1 Use Case #1. Identification and Benchmarking of new Buildings for hosting the electoral operations & provision of information for facilitating the smooth access to such facilities

The current process for the selection of the alternative voting venues to replace schools facilities is as follows:

- the competent office of the Municipality of Genoa, after consultation with other internal offices, prepares a list of the existing facilities alternative to the school premises where the electoral operations can be transferred. Such alternative facilities have to be consistent with a set of characteristics and dimensions previously defined, pursuant to the regulatory requirements.
- An institutional working group, composed of staff from the Ministry of the Interior, will select the new voting facilities, taking into account the following selection criteria:

- proximity of the new venues to the old voting venues in order not to create criticalities in the influx of voters;
- conditions of accessibility;
- compliance with the requirements established by the regulations regarding the structural characteristics of the election building (type of premises, dimensions, presence of common areas, service rooms, equipment, etc.).
- Information will be provided to the citizens in order both to inform them more fully about the new voting facilities and to facilitate an orderly and smooth access in line with health safety requirements. Besides information on the exact location of the relevant polling station, the voters will be informed about relevant aspects, such as the characteristics of the station (if it is a section for disabled access), the nearest AMT stops and the demographic offices.

3.2.2 Use Case #2. Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems.

The current process for the identification of the optimal allocation and management of human resources and other assets related to the Social Services Office and the Demographic/Registry Services Office includes:

- Analysis of the opportunities of interoperability of the sector-specific IT systems with wider systems (e.g. Regional or INPS DBs);
- Comparative analysis of the historical data on the allocation of human resources and other assets (e.g., machines, equipment, software/hardware) and creation of a data repository. For instance, as regards the Demographic/Registry Services Office, this comprises the analysis of the data related to the registry office changes (immigrations, changes of residence, changes in civil status, AIRE registrations, etc.) with the aim of channeling citizens' requests;
- Definition of strategic reading models of the collected data, with a specific territorialization and the possibility of longitudinal reading, as well as proposals for the re-engineering of the transversal work processes, the simplifying access to the portal for the citizens and the improvement of the ability to respond to citizens and of the internal communication between different offices, including the multi-purpose desk;
- Return of useful information to the public decision-maker, through exchange of documents and dedicated internal meetings to discuss the proper actions to be taken
- Communication initiatives towards the citizens.

3.2.3 Use Case #3. More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens’ Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations.

The current process regarding the provision of suggestions for the improvement of the livability of the City and/or for extraordinary maintenance interventions, as well as their handling, is conducted through the SegnalaCi platform, which can be also accessed via smartphone or tablet

Thanks to such platform, the citizens can make suggestions and reports to the Municipality of Genoa on a map (OpenStreetMap) in order to improve the quality of the services offered by the Administration itself and to improve the livability of the City, as well as to execute useful effective extraordinary maintenance interventions (on flowerbed borders, city squares and pedestrian areas, pavements and stairways, street mowing, etc.).

The citizen authenticates through Spid (public digital identity system) or registers for the first time and thus obtain username and password. The citizen can provide proposals, suggestions and reports on the map. In particular, there are two types of messages from the citizens:

- Suggestion, which means any proposal or communication, even of appreciation, by the citizen aimed at improving the quality of the services offered;

- Report, which means communication by the citizen regarding critical situations and / or malfunctions (e.g., signs, public lighting, holes in the streets, etc.).

The "report" is taken over by the municipal operators, who will forward to the responsible persons within 48 hours.

Such person will take care of proceeding with the necessary actions for solving the issue. If the requested or suggested intervention has been deemed useful, necessary and economically sustainable by the service manager, it will be included in the Administration's programs, on the basis of the priorities decided by the body itself and according to the methods and times defined independently by the Office.

The answer will be provided on average within 15 days.

With the official response from the institution, the report is closed.

Information about the type, location, handling times, citizen demographics etc. associated with each suggestion and report will be displayed and provided to both policy makers (inside the municipality) and citizens.

3.3 Related roles

The related roles per Use Case currently include:

Table 2. Genoa Pilot roles

Use Case #1	Use Case #2	Use Case # 3
Electoral Operation Department	Social Services Office	Civil Protection Department
Working group composed of staff from the Ministry of the Interior	Demographic/Registry Services Office	Mayor's Office
Agency for urban management	Public services department	IT Department
Mayor's Office	Mayor's Office	Extraordinary Interventions Office
IT Department	AIRE Agency	Facility management department
Public heritage Department	IT Department	Coordination of local districts department
Local security and police department	National and local healthy system	Agency for urban management
Citizens/ Voters	Citizens/ Residents	Office for Electrical Management
		Office for the Relations with the Public (URP)
		Citizens/ Residents

3.4 Future process improvements using AI4PP

3.4.1 Use Case #1. Identification and Benchmarking of new Buildings for hosting the electoral operations & provision of information for facilitating the smooth access to such facilities

Thanks to ML/DL techniques, indications will be extracted and, relying on the given criteria, recommendations will be provided on: i) the identification of the new election facilities, also with the aim of improving the service provided by the municipal offices during the elections, for example by arranging for the location of the voting offices near the offices that carry out support activities (in particular the issue of duplicate electoral cards, card update labels, etc.); ii) information to be provided to the citizens and other activities to facilitate an orderly and smooth access in line with health safety requirements;

Furthermore, thanks to the AI tools, exchange of knowledge between the different municipal offices and the proper consideration of the feedback/suggestions from the voters will be possible for identifying new locations, combined with the rationalization of the existing ones. In a complex urban area such as the City of Genoa, it is key to enhance the contribution of knowledge exchanges and a constant and effective relationship and consultation with the institutional bodies in the areas concerned, as well as to improve the provision of useful information and feedback gathering from the citizens in their role of voters. ML/DL techniques will be exploited in this direction as well: different configurations and options will be considered based on the data about citizens' and municipal offices' requests, their types and citizens' satisfaction feedback.

3.4.2 Use Case #2. Optimizing the Allocation and Use of Resources for Social and Demographic Services also via fostering the interoperability between information systems.

Thanks to AI4PublicPolicy it is expected to obtain a set of data-driven recommendations and rules about how to best allocate and use resources for the Demographic/Registry Services Office and Social Services Office and to enhance interoperability between information systems in order to make optimal use of resources, minimize service times and increase citizens' satisfaction.

3.4.3 Use Case #3. More effective extraordinary maintenance interventions by enhancing the “SegnalaCI” Citizens' Suggestions/Reports and Policies Visualizations.

Thanks to the use of AI4PublicPolicy tools, the SegnalaCi platform will be enriched with new improved functionalities, both regarding the handling of extraordinary interventions and the increase the transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of the policy development process, as well as the possible extension to cover the citizens' feedback on how their reports and/or suggestions have been addressed by the Municipality.

This will lead to the improvement of the planning and execution of the extraordinary maintenance interventions, as well as the outcomes and value of SegnalaCI Platform

The VPME will facilitate not only the creation/formulation of policies, but also their reprogramming and reconfiguration as well, including also organizational transformation activities.

4 Nicosia: Effective Policies for Holistic Mobility and Accessibility

4.1 Overview of the Use Case

Nicosia municipality has recently invested heavily in the development and deployment of a smart city platform, which will provide the means for integrating and analysing information from diverse sources (including sensors) throughout the city. This platform is an enabler for a paradigm shift in the way decisions are made i.e., a shift from semi-structured decisions to data-driven evidence-based policies. The mobility policies of the city provide a perfect case study for demonstrating this shift, given the existing fragmentation of relevant decisions. In this context, the goal of the pilot is to provide integrated mobility policies for citizens and for the city considering the viewpoints of different stakeholders and information from different systems. It also aims at paying emphasis to the mobility needs of elderly and disabled individuals based on the creation of policies tailored to their needs, including for examples policies for establishing “inclusiveness zones” in the city.

The pilot will enable the development of integrated, evidence-based policies for urban mobility, leveraging integrated data and information from previously siloed information such as information about the bus network of the city, and information about the parking spaces. The analysis of integrated data will be enabled by the AI4PP VPME environment, which will extend the capabilities of the smart city platform.

4.2 Relevant processes

The following figure (Figure 4) illustrates the “as-is” policy development process for urban mobility. The process involves the following (human & IT) actors:

- **Bus company:** The company that operates the city’s bus network. It possesses and manages information about the operation of the network, including bus routes, timetables, bus stops etc.
- **Ministry of transport:** The ministry of transport supervises the operation of the bus company and is a stakeholder in decisions about the operation of the buses.
- **City transport department:** The transport department of Nicosia municipality is a stakeholder in decisions that involve transportation and urban mobility in the city.
- **City healthcare department:** The healthcare department of the municipality is a stakeholder in decisions involving or affecting the citizens’ health and well-being.
- **Citizens:** Citizens can nowadays provide feedback (in various ways) about various mobility issues and policies. This feedback is integrated in software systems of the municipality. In the context of the as-is process illustration, we consider these systems as the city’s “ERP”.
- **City administration (top management):** The city administration interacts with all departments of the city and are in charge of the supervising and monitoring the municipality departments.
- **City council:** The main policy making body of the municipality. It takes decisions considering recommendations from the city administration, along with data and evidence that supports the various recommendations. (Mayor is the chair of the Municipal Council). The Mayor represents the municipality in a court of Law and before any state authority, and presides over all Council meetings, Administrative Committee meetings and any other municipal committee. He executes the Council’s decision and heads all municipal services which he directs and supervises.
- **Smart city platform:** The smart city platform is a quite new project that is currently operational based on a subset of information and process that what is envisaged in the future.

The policy making process involves information collection from “siloed” sources, which is not however automated and integrated. Information from the data sources flows selectively to different stakeholders. Hence, the various actors do not possess the same level and richness of information, which leads to information asymmetry and their inability to consider the viewpoints of other actors. Therefore, the city administration formulates policy proposals based on partial information and viewpoints that are far from being accurate and complete.

Figure 4. As-is Policy Making Process for Urban Mobility in the City of Nicosia

4.3 Related roles

In-line with the above-listed description of the process, the table below reviews the main roles entailed in the pilot.

Table 3. Nicosia Pilot roles

Stakeholder/Actor	Involvement in the Policy Making Process
Citizens / Inhabitants	Provide feedback on Mobility Policies (including complaints) based on established (electronic and non-electronic channels). The feedback is integrated in the city IT system.
Bus Network Operator	Operates the buses network of Nicosia and manage relevant information such as routes, frequencies, occupancy etc.
Ministry of Transport	Reviews and approves changes to the operation of the bus network
City Transport Department	Supervises the implementation of mobility policies within the city/municipality, while managing relevant information.
City Healthcare Department	Supervises the implementation of policies that affect the citizens' health and well-being. In the context of mobility policies their voice and intervention relates to policies about the mobility of elderly and disabled citizens.
City Administration	Consolidate policy proposals and present them to the City Council, along with relevant information. The latter may include evidence about the suitability of the policy, as well as the merit and need of a policy.

City Council	The top-level policy making body of the city, which develops and approves policies leveraging available information and evidence.
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4.4 Future process improvements using AI4PP

The following figure illustrates the “to-be” policy making process for urban mobility policies. This process is more integrated, and evidence-based thanks to the ability of the various stakeholders to access and analyse integrated information through a single-entry point. This point is the AI4PP VPME, which operates over integrated data available in the city platform. The decision-making process introduces a new role i.e., **the role of the data scientist / expert** that possesses the knowledge and skills to extract integrated policy-related insights from the data of the smart city platform and of the VPME.

City administration will take advantage of the data expert and of the VPME in order to provide accurate, timely, evidence-based policy making recommendations to the city council. These policy proposals will be justified based on data-driven insights from the analysis of the full range of available data. This will result in sharing a common view and common evidence across all stakeholders, as well as in the development of improved policies.

Figure 5. To-be Policy Making Process for Urban Mobility in the City of Nicosia

5 Lisbon: Energy Management and Optimization Policies

5.1 Overview of the Use Case

Name: **Renewables (PV) potential and performance analysis.**

Goal: To identify existing assets and assess the potential renewables (PV) production.

This use case aims to identify the PV systems existing in the city as well as create methods to assess and determine accurately their production potential. In a first stage, the goal will be to identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city in order to understand the current energy production performance in the city and infer about the city's PV adoption curve through time. These analytics should be made by using different available datasets, including orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available, as well as those provided by existing platforms (e.g., Solis platform).

In a second stage, this use case should provide users with the ability to monitor PV energy production potential, ideally by defining time series and forecast scenarios (e.g., on “day-ahead”; “month ahead”; “quarter ahead”, etc.). This aims to enable the definition of scenarios elucidating about the achievement of city's defined goals and targets for 2030, as well as to inform building(s) owner(s) and citizens about the potential PV production of their buildings and estimates about potential cost savings.

5.2 Relevant processes

The only process locally implemented was a manual identification of solar systems recurring to Google Maps aerial imagery visual scanning and pinpointing the respective latitude and longitude into a table, including eventual additional characteristics that the image allowed to infer. This procedure gave origin to the map of potential solar photovoltaic and solar thermal potential installations, which still requires thorough validation. Some of these pins can be validated by crosschecking with official data provided by the Directorate-General for Energy and Geology, or info provided by installers and owners, whereas others do require in-person and on-site verification.

Figure 6. Manual identification of solar systems in Lisbon

5.3 Related roles

The related roles per Use Case currently include:

Table 4. Lisbon Pilot roles

Public and local authorities
Citizen groups and associations
Research centres and academia
Companies and organizations of the sector

5.4 Future process improvements using AI4PP

The existing process, mentioned in 5.2, represents a very archaic first approach to the challenge. In this sense, we believe AI4PP platform could approach the issue in a more sophisticated and fast manner: the fast georeferentiation of potential solar systems; counting the number of panels in each one; distinguishing the photovoltaic technology from the thermal one, and from other rooftop elements; clustering priority locations for in-person and on-site validation; and the continuous update of the map using the most up-to-date available (public) datasets. This last aspect is of extreme importance, as it helps to monitor the evolution of the solar technology adoption in the city, and to understand to what degree the goals of Lisbon solar strategy are being met and what policies and measures should be put in place to leverage it.

6 Burgas: Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies

6.1 Overview of the Use Case

There are two use cases for the city of Burgas.

The first use case will measure water losses in the Pobeda neighbourhood and identify those that are due to unauthorized consumption. Subsequently, it will develop data-driven policies for the prevention of such losses.

The second use case will develop data-driven policies for the maintenance of main water infrastructure by monitoring and measuring the water inflow and the corresponding pressure on a continuous basis for the primary water distribution network along Industrialna street and the zone around it. The data will be analysed to help plan maintenance and repair operations so that they cause minimal disruption to service.

6.2 Relevant processes

Currently the policy-making processes involve decisions at management level with input from end users in the form of signals and complaints, from engineers regarding the technical requirements of the work, and from finance experts with regards to the available budget. When the work involves municipal infrastructure, experts from Burgas municipality with the relevant expertise are also involved.

The maintenance tasks itself are carried out by maintenance teams and overseen by engineers of the Water Utility company. The company also has a PR department in charge of direct communication with the public. Once the work is done, end users can send feedback about the new quality of water services, so the process may be represented by the following diagram.

Figure 7. Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies in Burgas

6.3 Related roles

The stakeholders for these processes include:

Table 5. Burgas Pilot roles

End users of the water utility company services (citizens, businesses, industries)
Community leaders , including local mayoral representatives, whose aim is the welfare of the members of their community and neighbourhood.

Municipality experts , whose aim is for the city of Burgas to offer good quality of life to its residents, including access to clean, modern, and affordable water supply.
Water utility company engineers , who oversee the installation, maintenance, and repair work
Water utility company quality managers , who control the quality of services
Water utility company executives , who authorise the maintenance projects, replacement works
Water utility company finance experts , who will ensure that the work done is according to budget
Water utility company communication experts , who are the link between the customers and the company

6.4 Future process improvements using AI4PP

Currently communication and processing of end user signals and complaints is time-consuming and cumbersome. The introduction of AI will make the process more automated and hence faster. It will also improve the quality of services by minimizing human judgement areas and by allowing for the synchronization of maintenance work with other infrastructural projects, e.g., road construction or road maintenance works, planned by the municipality.

Additionally, in the first case, data coming from end users regarding water consumption and pipe bursts is often unreliable. The use of AI will improve the reliability of the data and increase the transparency of the policy-making process, which is key in dealing with sensitive issues such as unauthorized water consumption, especially in an area as the chosen neighbourhood, Pobeda, an area with a largely marginalized population. Moreover, AI will also reduce the time required to fix a pipe burst or detecting an unauthorized water consumption thus reducing the nonrevenue water and preserving the water resources of the city.

7 Conclusions

D2.4 “Policy making processes blueprints V1”, has been authored within the framework of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”, following the co-creation methodology and participatory design approach that involves all relevant stakeholders. The purpose of D2.4 is to capture the existing processes from the five pilot cities of AI4PP, i.e. Athens, Lisbon, Nicosia, Genoa and Burgas, in relation to the use cases that will form the basis for the pilot activities within the project. Initial ideas on how said processes could be enhanced and improved through the proposed AI solutions are also included per city.

This is the first of two versions this document will be delivered in. The document was edited and resubmitted following the first review meeting according to the comments received by the reviewers and the Project Officer. Subsequent versions will also include blueprints for reengineering policy making processes and supporting employees of the public administration accordingly, also capturing the interactions between different roles in the public administration domain as well as between public administrators and the local ecosystem.